

IMPLEMENTING DIFFERENT TEACHING METHODS IN THE ENGLISH CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the importance of various methods in teaching English language and illustrates main ideas with solid examples. Several types of approved and beneficial methods' names and their roles in language teaching are also provided in this article.

My full name is Oblaqulova Dinora. I was born in 2004 in Samarkand region in Uzbekistan. In 2020, I was holder of CEFR B2 . In 2021, I enrolled for the Uzbekistan State World Languages University with 189 score as a Candidate for the President Scholarship and I am author of many articles in English and Uzbek languages. I got 7 band from the IELTS exam in 2022.

In our modern world, English language plays a vital role around the world and young people are doing their best to learn this global language. The main reason is that being fluent in this language opens many doors to youth: they can boost their careers and can work in many reputable foreign companies which provide their employees with high salaries. In this case, not only in Uzbekistan, but also all around the world school children are being taught the English from their early ages and they are also continuing studying this language both at high schools and at universities. To make the learning process easy and enjoyable several beneficial methods are being implemented in the English classrooms by teachers. With the help of those methods, students acquire language easily in a relaxed English atmosphere.

Teaching method serve as a tool that can aid teachers who teach foreign languages. By knowing many methods, teachers can choose to teach differently from their old teaching styles. Throughout the history of teaching languages a number of teaching approaches have been tried and some of them became popular and effective than others. In this article we will be familiar with some of them.

The first one is the Direct Method. It is not a new method and it has been very popular during many years. It has one main rule: no translations are allowed, because with the aid of this method visual materials are demonstrated without any translation from students' native languages. For instance, if teacher explains a new theme about the natural life and its habitat, he can use the picture of forest with its animals in it on a large blackboard. With the help of those images pupils can be able to learn new words and phrases without translating them. When questions are asked, teacher again answers by drawing pictures on the board in a detailed way. This method works well for youth who perceive information visually with a little effort and this leads them to be successful in the learning process.

The second one is called Grammar Translation Method which relies a lot on translation and as its name suggests it focuses mainly on the grammar. This method is helpful for those students who wish to study language at a deeper level. Teacher deals with the rules of grammar with students and do exercises in a collaboration. The main purpose of this method is being informed about all grammar rules and being able to translate a number of sentences directly from the English language. After completing the course with this method, language learners will be familiar with all tenses types, logical connectors & discourse markers, position of adverbials and the use of propositions in sentences.

The next successful method is called Audio-Lingual Method. It is an oral based approach. If we observe the English class where this method is used, we can notice that students listen carefully to their teachers speaking in the English or reading a new dialogue between foreigners. Then, all students repeat after the teacher several times and correct their pronunciation mistakes: putting word stress, compound stress and phrase stress correctly. Students would be able to take notes while repeating. In order to enhance the oral skills, the teacher and students may take part in answer-question sessions. For instance, the teacher may ask each student in turn, "Where did you go on the weekend?" and then the students ought to answer truthfully: "I went to the cinema or theatre". Home assignment should be based on Audio-Lingual Method. Pupils should prepare their own dialogues with their parents or siblings. When checking home tasks, teacher ought to pay attention to the punctuation which creates correct intonation. The important point about this method is its result. After the English classes, students develop a pronunciation style which is understandable and clear to both native and non-native speakers.

The additional method is Task – Based Language Learning. The main materials of this method are exercises and tasks. This works for many students because interesting and relevant tasks are given by the teacher, and the students are asked to complete them according to their knowledge of English. Once the task is complete, teacher analyses the main grammar and spelling mistakes of each student. There is an example of the process of task-based language learning lesson below:

1. Pre-Task;
2. Task (includes presentation, planning and task);
3. Review from teacher.

But tasks are given to the language learners according to their level of English. There are provided two sentences with different levels as an example below:

1. John is playing with his car;

2. John, who is a little boy, is playing with his car.

The last successful method is the Lexical Approach. This method is based on vocabulary acquisition and analyzing lexical chunks in the English language. Students are asked to read paragraphs or texts and to analyze them with the help of the dictionaries. Instead of focusing on grammatical structures, lexical resource will be in the focus. By doing so, pupils are able to examine how lexical phrases and chunks of language play an important role in producing fluent English speech. In this approach, there are several types of lexical items, such as:

1. Words (flower);
2. Polywords (by the way);
3. Collocations (fast food);
4. Institutionalized utterances (that'll do);
5. Sentence frames and heads (this is not as easy as you think);
6. Text frames (In this article we will analyze...; First of all...).

At the end of the course, lexical approach gives the opportunity to understand all English words and phrases without any dictionary to students.

To conclude, learning foreign languages is the necessity of our contemporary world. If teachers convey information to students in an informative and interesting manner, language learning will be an easy process in the reality. With the help of different approaches, students can achieve their desired success in language learning. Mentioned five methods can assist language learners to acquire the English easily. In order to improve efficiency in the learning process, teachers ought to implement one of those approaches in collaboration with their students. By using those mentioned methods, tutors not only teach the foreign languages in the most accurate detailed way, but also they will be able to get the best results in a short period of time.

References:

1. Diane L.F and Marti A. "Techniques & Principles in Language Teaching". T., Oxford University Press, 2011.
2. Dionysios I. Psoinos. "Adapting Approaches and Methods to Teaching English Online". T., Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2021.
3. R.K. Satya. "Modern methods of teaching English". T., A P H Publishing Corporation, 2008.
4. <http://www.huntesl.com/a-brief-look-at-the-different-esl-teaching-approaches-and-methods/>
5. <https://learnenglish100.com/esl-teaching-methods/>
6. <https://www.getmyuni.com/articles/methods-of-teaching-english>